

ISSN 2230-7850

INDIAN STREAMS RESEARCH JOURNAL

International Recognition Multidisciplinary Research Journal

Volume - 5 | Issue - 6 | July - 2015

Impact Factor : 3.1560(UIF)

DOI Prefix 10.9780/22307850

UNDERSTANDING RITUAL AS RITUALISATION AND PRAXIS

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ABSTRACT:- Ritual has been understood variedly by different scholars, according to the context of the ritual. Still a holistic approach towards understanding ritual theoretically is very much lacking, though scholars have studied and elaborated the individual rituals performed in different regions and places.

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Indian Streams Research Journal

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UNDERSTANDING RITUAL AS RITUALISATION AND PRAXIS

M. P. Terence Samuel¹ and Gargi Mukherjee²

“No people could live without first esteeming; but if they want to preserve themselves, then they must not esteem as the neighbor esteems. Much that was good to one people was scorn and infamy to another: thus I found it. Much I found called evil here, and decked out with purple honors there...

A tablet of the good hangs over every people. Behold, it is the tablet of their overcomings; behold, it is the voice of their will to power.

Praiseworthy is whatever seems difficult to a people; whatever seems indispensable and difficult is called good; and whatever liberates even out of the deepest need, the rarest, the most difficult – that they call holy.

Whatever makes them rule and triumph and shine, to the awe and envy of their neighbors, that is to them the high, the first, the measure,

ABSTRACT

Ritual has been understood variedly by different scholars, according to the context of the ritual. Still a holistic approach towards understanding ritual theoretically is very much lacking, though scholars have studied and elaborated the individual rituals performed in different regions and places. But Catherine Bell, in her works on ritual, attempts to provide a theoretical understanding of ritual of all genres. She takes up different theoretical tools already available in the field of knowledge of different subjects and applies them to understand the nature of ritual theoretically.

Here an attempt has been made by the authors as to how to understand ritual as a process of ritualisation where ritualised social bodies interact, reproduce and recreate social spaces through rituals. Further, Bell understands ritual as praxis where theory and practice are in a dialectical movement, where the one reifies the other perpetually, through the means of tradition and social bodies involving power relations too.

KEYWORDS : Catherine Bell, Ritualisation, Practice, Social Body, Hegemony and Power.

Short Profile

M. P. Terence Samuel is working as an Assistant Professor at Department of Philosophy & Comparative Religion in Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan, West Bengal.

delve deep into the subject in order to understand its relation with the construction of collective consciousness. In recent years, diverse fields, ranging from history to

the meaning of all things...

Verily, men gave themselves all their good and evil. Verily, they did not take it, they did not find it, nor did it come to them as a voice from heaven. Only man placed values in things to preserve himself – he alone created a meaning for things, a human meaning...”

- Nietzsche (Thus Spake Zarathustra)

INTRODUCTION

Since the advent of colonialism, the anthropological studies of ritual came to the fore. Especially, the ritual studies done by Robertson Smith, McLennan, Durkheim and Frazer kindled the interests of the researchers to

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